

TWO OPEN ACCESS DATASETS OF USER GENERATED AUDIO RECORDINGS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this document is to present two open access datasets with user generated audio recordings. The provided audio files originate from two different public events, a musical concert and a football match. Also, for each event, we provide two different types of collections; the original unorganized collection of uncompressed audio files and an additional organized collection, where the different recordings corresponding to similar parts of the event are grouped into specific folders and time-aligned so they can be played back in unison. Below, we describe the way that this data was acquired in each event and the way that it can be useful in the context of research related to content-based multimedia management as well as to research related to mixing, enhancement and reproduction of user generated audio.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the proliferation of smart-phones and portable electronic devices, more and more of us become engaged in the process of capturing and sharing audiovisual content from public events that we attend. Such content can be very valuable to the broadcasters and producers as it may enrich the professional footage or provide coverage for parts of the event that have not been captured by the professional equipment. Yet, it is not trivial to organize this content in a way that it can be usable for the said purpose. For example, as user generated content lacks metadata which is informative about the exact location and time of recording, it would require enormous time and effort from the professional editor to manually search for videos referring to a particular segment of the event, or to group and temporally align multiple videos overlapping in space and time.

Fortunately, as several works have demonstrated in the past, it is possible to automatically organize such content by exploiting the correlations in the audio streams available in the User Generated Video (UGV) collection. Of fundamental importance for succeeding in this task is to employ audio features which are robust to different kinds of channel varia-

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Fig. 1. Picture of the concert taken from one of the user generated videos.

tions – as for example environmental noise, different recording locations, varying frequency response of each recording device, etc – and which at the same time allow for fast mining through large collections containing hundreds or thousands of UGVs. Respecting these requirements, audio fingerprinting techniques, originally designed for the purpose of song identification [1–3], have been successfully employed from researchers working on the management of user generated content in the past [4–8]. Being successful in this organization task, one may then exploit the result of automatic organization to produce a linear plot with multiple visual perspectives of the same event [5], or may combine the audio streams from the different devices in order to produce a new acoustic sequence of increased duration [8] and enhanced quality [9, 10].

In this document, we describe the contents of two different open access audio datasets [11]; one generated from users attending a musical concert and one from users attending a football match taking place inside a crowded open stadium. For each type of event, we provide an organized and an unorganized collection. We describe how the recordings were generated in each event and the usefulness of each collection (organized and unorganized) in terms of research related to content-based multimedia indexing and organization as well as to research related to automatic mixing, enhancement and reproduction of user generated audio.

Fig. 2. Picture of the stadium taken from one of the videos generated by user “giorgos” at location 2.

2. COLLECTION

There were 9 and 5 subjects participating in the data collection process in the concert and the athletic event respectively. In each type of public event, the recording process was performed in an organized fashion. In particular, the instruction given in the case of the concert was to capture a 2 or 3 minute long video during particular songs, while for the case of the athletic event, a 2 or 3 minute long video every 10 minutes was requested, with the first recording starting at the official kick-off time of the game. This was necessary in order to ensure a minimum overlap across recordings associated with the same part of the event. Nevertheless, the exact time of initiation of each recording varied arbitrarily from one device to the other. In total 60 and 50 audio recordings were acquired for the concert and the football match respectively.

Some additional details about the recording process are as follows. For the athletic event, 5 participants contributed video recordings using their smart-phones. Their locations, which are numbered from 1 to 5 in Fig. 3, were fixed all the time. Throughout almost the entire duration of the game, a big part of the crowd was chanting, mainly following the organized fans of the hosting team, distributed at the north side of the stadium, as shown in Fig. 3. On the other hand, the data in the music event was extracted from 9 different recording devices, at locations which were static during each song but which varied from one song to the other. The public address system located at the left and right side of the stage, represented the most dominant acoustic source during the concert.

After extraction and conversion to PCM (.wav) format each audio file was renamed so that its name is indicative about the part of the event that it belongs to. Furthermore, the naming convention is indicative about the relations between different audio files. For example, in the concert database *song3dev3* and *song3dev9* are recordings of the same song captured from different devices, and as expected, these two recordings overlap in time. Similarly, for the football match collection, recordings *17_20_dp* and *17_20_fil* were produced approximately during the same time (i.e. 17.20 local time) and therefore also overlap in time. On the contrary, files

Fig. 3. Sketch of the stadium with corresponding recording locations denoted with black dots.

song3dev6 and *song2dev6* originate from the same device but are captured during different parts of the performance. In both sessions, all audio streams belonging to the same folder contain mutually overlapping regions and the average duration of overlap is equal to 2 minutes approximately (with some pairs however exhibiting significantly less overlap durations). The only exception for the case of the concert is file *song2dev9* which does not overlap with files *song2dev8* and *song2dev2*, due to the fact that the particular recording ended before the two others begun (this particular case is also shown in Fig. 4). Similarly, in the football match collection there are two recordings, *16_44_stavros* and *18_58_stavros*, which do not match with any other recording since they were the only ones captured at that particular instant. Finally, the names given to the football match recordings are indicative about the location in the stadium, as shown in the right half of Fig. 3.

2.1. Unorganized collection

This is basically the original, unprocessed collection of user generated audio recordings obtained in each event, provided in .wav format. All audio files are available at 48 kHz sampling rate and coded at 16 bit. Each audio file may be available as mono or stereo audio stream, depending on the original format that the content was captured from each device. The duration and time of initiation of each recording varies arbitrarily from one recording to the other. This collection is thus ideal for research related to content-based multimedia management and indexing by exploiting correlations in the audio modality. Example of such tasks are

- automating audio matching,
- automating audio synchronization,
- event-based media processing and retrieval,
- audio (speech, music, etc) content extraction.

Fig. 4. Preview of an organized collection (*song2*) imported inside a digital audio work-station (Cubase).

2.2. Organized collection

In contrast to the unorganized collection, all audio streams here are grouped into specific folders and are provided in monophonic format. For example, in the concert collection, all recordings initiated during the 4th song of the band are located in folder *song4*. Similarly, folder *1710* contains all audio recordings that the participants started capturing around 17.10 local time in the stadium. Apart from organizing the collection into separate folders, each audio recording was processed in order to assist its synchronization with respect to the other recordings in the same folder. Specifically, each track is padded with a silent segment at the beginning in order to compensate for the different recording initiation times. When these audio clips are imported into a multitrack Digital Audio Workstation such as Cubase or Audacity, they are automatically synchronized with one another as shown in Fig. 4. This way, all the contents of a folder can be played in unison and panned to different directions in order to transmit a monophonic, stereophonic or surround experience to the listener. Additionally, different mixing strategies can be investigated as the means to enhance (suppress) desired (undesired) content and to improve the overall acoustic representation in general.

We note here that for time-aligning the recordings in each folder we have used an automatic fingerprint cross-correlation process. For organizing the concert collection, we have used the fingerprinting technique described in [2]. On the other hand, a special type of fingerprint was designed for the football match collection [12], as it was found that state of the art fingerprinting techniques were incapable for performing a correct organization of such content.

3. CONCLUSION

User generated recordings from two different types of public events are provided as open access data in the form of an organized and an unorganized collection. The unorganized collec-

tion is optimal for investigating tasks related to audio database management and indexing. On the other hand, the organized collection, grouping and synchronization of the content has been performed beforehand, making this collection ideal for investigating tasks related to the mixing and reproduction of multichannel audio based on user generated recordings.

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